

OCEAN:ICE News – January 2024

OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN:ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Happy New Year!

As we bid farewell to 2023, we celebrate the publication of the first OCEAN:ICE paper and the success of our multiple climate coffee sessions, a tradition we're eager to continue in the coming months.

Stepping into 2024, our team is actively engaged in exciting fieldwork activities. We're currently navigating the challenges of deploying Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUV) in the Amundsen Sea (MS3) and intricately placing instruments through the Fimbul Ice Shelf borehole (MS4), as well as deploying Argo floats in the Amundsen and Ross Seas (MS1).

The new year also brings exciting initiatives and events, such as the launch of the "Explain it in Two Ways" video series in collaboration with PolarRES and OCEAN:ICE and Arctic PASSION policy briefing.

Enjoy this month's happenings and we'll see you in February with more exciting updates!

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN:ICE Activities

First OCEAN:ICE Paper Published

A number of OCEAN:ICE project members, led by [Dr Alessandro Silvano](#) from the [University of Southampton](#), co-authored a review article on [observing Antarctic Bottom Water \(AABW\) in the Southern Ocean](#).

The lead author Alessandro Silvano explains the key purpose of the review article:

"Here we review how to observe Antarctic Bottom Water: the densest, coldest and deepest water mass in the ocean. It originates near Antarctica and spreads throughout the global ocean abyss. Antarctic Bottom Water "traps" vast amounts of carbon away from the atmosphere for centuries, thus regulating Earth's climate on long time scales. In this article we highlight key outstanding scientific questions related to Antarctic Bottom Water. We propose a coordinated observing system capable of answering those questions, exploiting new technologies such as underwater robots and satellite sensors as well as Artificial Intelligence. An international and sustained effort is needed to understand Antarctic Bottom Water if we aim to reliably predict and adapt to global warming over the next decades and centuries."

Mertz Glacier front (East Antarctica): one of the few locations where Antarctic Bottom Water originates. Credit: Alessandro Silvano

Keep an eye out for new OCEAN:ICE papers which will be listed on our [Scientific Publications](#) page.

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. Further down in the *Upcoming Climate Coffees* section you may find the busy lineup for upcoming Climate Coffees in 2024, and if you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

"Explain it in Two Ways" Video Series in Collaboration with PolarRES

We're thrilled to share an exciting collaboration between [OCEAN:ICE](#) and [PolarRES](#) – the launch of a new series, "[Explain it in Two Ways](#)"!

Five of our researchers are breaking down complex scientific processes for both the general public and scientific audience.

In the first [episode](#) Ruth Mottram, OCEAN:ICE project coordinator, explains what surface mass balance means and its importance in Polar research. The second video explores the topic of coupled climate models, featuring researchers Clara Lambin and Damien Maure. Last but not least, in the final episode of the series, Ruth Price and Ella Gilbert demystify the term: mixed-phase clouds.

Make sure to keep an eye on OCEAN:ICE and PolarRES social media platforms this January to catch the episodes!

 PolarRES

**EXPLAIN IT
IN TWO WAYS**
VIDEO SERIES

 OCEAN:ICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation

 The PolarRES project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme call H2020-LC-CLA-2018-2019-2020 under grant agreement Nr. 101003590

OCEAN:ICE and Arctic PASSION Policy Briefing

Join us on the 24th of January 2024 from 14:15 to 16:00 (CET) for the [OCEAN:ICE](#) and [Arctic PASSION](#) policy briefing '[From changing Polar regions to policy responses – Strengthening EU and global climate preparedness](#)' at the European Parliament and online.

Advancing polar scientific research and well-coordinated observations, dissemination and open access to knowledge are key components of the decision making process. As attention in Europe and across the globe turns increasingly towards the Poles, European projects including OCEAN:ICE and Arctic PASSION aim to present/illustrate status and implications of their current research and observation activities to highlight impacts on the European Union and beyond. This event will showcase the latest findings of OCEAN:ICE and Arctic PASSION on how changes in the polar regions impact European climate, infrastructure and livelihoods.

Visit our [website](#) for more information.

JOIN US AT

OCEAN:ICE and Arctic PASSION Policy Briefing

From Changing Polar Regions to Policy Responses – Strengthening EU and Global Climate Preparedness

24 January 2024 | European Parliament & online

 OCEAN:ICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation

 ARCTIC PASSION is funded by funded by the European Union, Horizon 2020 Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101003472

EU Programme for Climate Change
Euföröngi og Stöðvæðis Færsluáætt

Workshop on Anomalous Freshwater for Climate Models

On the 12th and 13th of February 2024, various members of the OCEAN:ICE community are going to participate in a virtual workshop, organised by [Dr. Gavin A. Schmidt](#), on defining ice sheet freshwater fluxes as boundary conditions for coupled climate models.

The workshop is going to draw together various scientists from multiple projects, initiatives, and groups. It will consist of pre-recorded talks from the invited speakers, interactive discussion groups, regional breakout groups, and three short global online video calls.

If you are interested in taking part in the workshop, you may register your interest [here](#).

Upcoming Climate Coffees

[Emmanuele Russo](#) on [Increasing Intensity of Extreme Heatwaves: The Crucial Role of Metrics](#)

15 February 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CET).

Register [here](#).

The poster features the 'Climate Coffee' logo on the left, consisting of four wavy lines in blue, dark blue, light blue, and gold. To the right of the logo, the text 'Climate Coffee' is written in a large, bold, black sans-serif font. Further right is a cluster of dark brown coffee beans. Below the logo and title, the speaker's name 'Emmanuele Russo, ETH Zürich' is listed. The title of the talk is 'Increasing Intensity of Extreme Heatwaves: The Crucial Role of Metrics'. The date and time are '15 February 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CET' and 'Online'. At the bottom, there are logos for the Danish Meteorological Institute, ECRA, OCEAN:ICE, and the European Union. A small text block on the right side of the bottom row states: 'OCEANICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation'.

Climate Coffee

Emmanuele Russo, ETH Zürich

Increasing Intensity of Extreme Heatwaves: The Crucial Role of Metrics

15 February 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CET
Online

 OCEANICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation

[Bijan Fallah](#) on [Efforts on the Downscaling of CMIP6 Models](#)

22 February 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CET).

Register [here](#).

The poster features the 'Climate Coffee' logo on the left, consisting of four wavy lines in blue, dark blue, light blue, and gold. To the right of the logo, the text 'Climate Coffee' is written in a large, bold, black sans-serif font. Further right is a cluster of dark brown coffee beans. Below the logo and title, the speaker's name 'Bijan Fallah, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK)' is listed. The title of the talk is 'Efforts on the downscaling of CMIP6 models'. The date and time are '22 February 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CET' and 'Online'.

Climate Coffee

Bijan Fallah, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK)

Efforts on the downscaling of CMIP6 models

22 February 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CET
Online

[Matthias Röthlisberger](#) on [Quantifying the physical processes leading to atmospheric hot extremes at a global scale](#)

7 March 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CET).

Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Matthias Röthlisberger, ETH Zürich

**Quantifying the physical processes leading to
atmospheric hot extremes at a global scale**

7 March 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CET
Online

OCEANICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation

Happening in Winter

OCEAN:ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 24 January 2024, OCEAN:ICE and Arctic PASSION Policy Briefing, [From changing Polar regions to policy responses – Strengthening EU and global climate preparedness](#), European Parliament and online
- 12-13 February 2024, Workshop on Anomalous Freshwater for Climate Models, online
- 18-23 February 2024, [Ocean Sciences Meeting](#), New Orleans

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN:ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

Are you following us on Social Media?

Stay up to date with OCEAN:ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

Who is OCEAN:ICE?

OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN:ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

Danish
Meteorological
Institute

**Northumbria
University**
NEWCASTLE

**UNIVERSITY OF
LIVERPOOL**

OCEAN:ICE is co-funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation